

Research

DESIGN OF A BASE-ISOLATION SYSTEM FOR SEISMIC PROTECTION OF BUILDINGS ACCORDING TO SEISMIC ZONE FACTOR OF INDIA

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Abstract: A practical solution to avoid structural damage in building during earthquakes involves the use of base isolation, which consists of decoupling the superstructure from its foundation to reduce transmission of seismic waves from the ground into the structure. The main objective of this paper is to develop a new seismic isolation device containing rubber, steel and spring as well which will react resistive in nature during earthquake and can bare lateral and vertical displacement too which as result will not affect the structure of a building. Device contains mild steel sheet of 2.06% carbon, up to 1.65% of manganese, up to 0.5% of silicon and sulphur and phosphorus as impurities, a die springs which are made up of rectangular wire instead of circular, unlike their 'compression' counterparts, a elastomer (rubber) sheet named as KL301 which have Shear modulus of 4300 kPa and the thickness sheet is 20mm with diameter of 182mm are used. Test are on simulation based on sliding condition (earthquake resistive building) and on non-sliding condition (earthquake non-resistive building). The seismic isolation device, which is placed on the plinth level, consists of outer steel plate, rubber plate, inner steel plate and spring braces. Spring box allows for free support of the structure in terms of (1) They can control movement in all directions, (2) They can retain deformation in all directions, (3) They can bare horizontal as well as vertical forces (wind, earthquake) on the structure of a building. As a result of simulation by linear dynamic possessing random vibration and response spectrum analysis test on both the building the mass participation were different on both the building which shows that a building without base isolation system have more damage compared to building with a base isolation device by approx. 27% difference.

Keywords: Base isolation device, sliding and non-sliding conditions, solid works linear dynamic test, response spectrum analysis, stress and displacement, mass participation difference.

Introduction

The simplest way to isolate the superstructure from the substructure is to decouple them by providing a sliding interface in between. The relative movement across this interface during an earthquake would restrict transmission of seismic waves to the superstructure by dissipating some part of the input seismic energy in friction. It is easy to provide a distributed isolation system arranged uniformly around the structure's base in the form of continuous layer at plinth level (instead of a number of friction bearings at discrete locations) during normal construction. Now as per the seismic condition of India it has more than 50% area in the country is considered prone to damaging earthquakes. The north-eastern locale of the nation just as the whole Himalayan belt is powerless to extraordinary tremors of size more than 8.0. The primary driver of tremors in these areas is because of the development of the Indian plate towards the Eurasian plate at the pace of around 50 mm for each year. Indian subcontinent has endured the absolute most noteworthy seismic tremors on the planet with extent surpassing 8.0. For example, in a limited capacity to focus around 50 years, such quakes happened: Assam seismic tremor of 1897 (greatness 8.7) (Oldham, 1899), Kangra tremor of 1905 (size 8.6) (Middlemiss, 1910), Bihar-Nepal earthquake of 1934 (magnitude 8.4) (GSI, 1939), and the Assam-Tibet earthquake of 1950 (magnitude 8.7) (CBG, 1953), Kutch earthquake of 26 January 2001 (M_w 7.6–7.7), Kashmir earthquake of 2005 ($7.6M_w$), Gujarat earthquake of 2007 ($5.1M_w$), Uttarakhand earthquake of 2017 (5.1 magnitude). This paper focuses on Kutch earthquake of 26 January 2001 analysis. Designing of earthquake resistive building due to included study on base isolation system used in past is very important. The concept of base isolation as an application of the period shifting technique is now widely accepted in earthquake-prone areas of the India for protecting important structures from strong ground motions. For an earthquake of unanticipated intensity, it is acceptable that the structure suffers significant damage, but it must not collapse. Under earthquake action which slightly exceeds the intensity for which the system was designed, this added spring box will suffice to limit the response of the isolation system to levels of relative horizontal as well as vertical displacement. Multiple die compression-type springs are positioned in a special square-shaped box to obtain a symmetrical response in tension and compression-type axial loading.

For seismic tremor safe development utilizing base disengagement [1]. It was discovered that more consideration ought to be paid to four focuses:

1. Readiness of rules for assessment and endorsement of base separation structures,
2. Readiness of rules identified with the exhibition of base detachment gadgets,
3. Offices to energize trade, assortment and scattering of specialized data on the reaction control structure,
4. Investigation of strategies for assessment of execution of reaction control structures.

The currently commercially available isolator bearings are either circular or longitudinal-shaped. Distributed isolators in the form of long strips would have distinct advantages over square or circular isolators when applied to structures where the lateral-resisting system comprises walls. The most attractive features of friction base-isolation systems are their effectiveness over a wide range of frequency input, and that the maximum acceleration transmissibility is limited by the maximum limiting frictional force[2]. An average reduction in maximum response accelerations and maximum base shear by approximately 30 and 40%, respectively, was obtained in the isolated structure as compared with the structure without base isolation. [3] Experimented with low-friction materials as sliding joints to ensure building safety during strong earthquakes. There has been significant amount of numerical investigation on the performance of pure-friction sliding systems under harmonic and earthquake type excitation in the past by[2], [4], [5], [6], and so on. Chia-Ming and Billie F. presented development and exploratory check of a functioning base separation framework for a seismically energized building and displaying the mind-boggling nature of control-structure cooperation (CSI) [7]. Hyung-Jo et al explored a shrewd base-confinement framework utilizing magneto rheological (MR) elastomers, which are another class of keen materials whose versatile modulus or solidness can be balanced relying upon the size of the applied attractive field. The outcomes further propose that the achievability of utilizing MR elastomers as factor firmness components for improving the exhibition of regular base-disengagement frameworks [8]. Because of the generally low damping property of common elastic (LDRB), beneficial damping gadgets may likewise be utilized [9]. Be that as it may, high damping elastic orientation (HDRB) have huge relocation and damping limits [10] and they are one of the most prudent and powerful seismic isolators [11]. Calabrese (2013) built up a minimal effort base confinement innovation dependent on reused elastic. It can be concluded from the

chronological review that few studies directly practiced on the isolation device for vibration control of buildings.

The main objective of this paper is to develop a new seismic isolation device containing rubber, steel and spring as well which will react resistive in nature during earthquake and can bare lateral and vertical displacement too which as result will not affect the structure of a building. The seismic isolation device, which is placed on the plinth level of the house, consists of outer steel plate, rubber plate, inner steel plate and spring braces in both vertical and horizontal direction. Bearing allows for stress-free support of the structure in terms of (1) they can rotate in all directions, (2) they can retain deformation in all directions, (3) they take horizontal forces (wind, earthquake).

Materials and methods

New spring coupling principle and parameter value:

A specially designed device with a multiple die compression-type springs, mild steel plates, a natural elastomer of good quality have been designed to obtain a symmetrical response in tension and compression-type axial loading in a structure. Spring- box have much better unique property compared to base isolation devices used before in a building.

Spring-box

Specimen and material of spring box:

Number	Name of part	Dimension	Material	Quantity
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1	Cover plate-1	445×285×60	S.S.304	2
2	Cover plate	385×285×60	S.S.304	2
3	Outer plate	445×445×30	S.S.304	2
4	Mid-rubber	445×445×50	KL301	2
5	Inner plate	325×325×30	S.S.304	2
6	Spring guide	φ72×φ62×68 WITH 30MM CUT	M.S	8
7	Spring	ND=φ50, WD=φ7	S.S.304	4

DIE SPRING:

Similar to compression springs, die springs are manufactured and built to take a higher load than other springs. These sorts of springs are made with rectangular wire rather than round, dissimilar to their 'pressure' partners. This kind of high-power pressure spring can deal with 30% more than a standard pressure spring. The utilization of rectangular and square wire is the prime component that gives the bite the dust spring its remarkable property, and it is this bigger mass which gives the spring a more noteworthy power. Kick the bucket springs are an amazingly dependable and predictable spring.

Number of springs: 4

Number of turns: 9

MILD STEEL:

Carbon steels are ironcarbon amalgams which contain up to 2.06 percent of carbon, up to 1.6percentof manganese, up to 0.5 percent of silicon and sulphur and phosphorus as degradation. Carbon content in carbon steel decides its quality and flexibility. The higher carbon content, the higher steel quality and the lower its flexibility. Carbon steel is presently the most widely recognized type of steel since its cost is generally low while it gives material properties that are satisfactory for some applications. There were two layers of sheets divided into two parts as inner steel plate and outer steel plate and specification of them are as follows:

Density: 7.85 g/cm³

Young's modulus: 200 Gpa

This is the inner plate on which four spring guides are placed.

KL301 RUBBER SHEET: A sheet made up from the blend of high damping rubber is used in the box. The intensify, a high damping elastomer, is called KL301 and is made by the Bridgestone Corporation Limited, Japan. KL301 has a shear modulus decreases to 650 kPa at 50% strain, to 430 kPa at 100% strain and 340 kPa at 150% strain.

Shear modulus: 4300 kPa

Number of sheets: 2

Design axial pressure: 3.23 Mpa

Type of joints:

Joints between two plates and rubber is bonded connection in a terms of simulation.

Joint between spring guide and inner plate is single phase joint. Preferred single phase joint because this type of joint is used for super-structures to achieve super strength in a structure. If we use welding joint there casting will be required which can cause crack in a welding joint and result into weakness of a spring box.

DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF BASE ISOLATED STRUCTURES: Generally, the base isolated buildings are designed such that the superstructure above isolators and base structure below isolators remain elastic and non-linearity is contained within the isolators. The equations of motion used are as follows:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku = -MR(\ddot{u}_g + \ddot{u}_b) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$R^T M\ddot{u} + R(\ddot{u}_g + \ddot{u}_b) + M_b(\ddot{u}_g + \ddot{u}_b) + C_b\dot{u}_b + K_b u_b + f + f_c = 0 \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Where M, C and K are super structure mass, damping and solidness lattices individually in the fixed base condition,

R = Influence network,

$\ddot{u}$, $\dot{u}$ and u = the floor quickening, speed and uprooting vectors separately, comparative with the base,

$\ddot{u}_b$ = Vector of base quickening comparative with the ground,

$\ddot{u}_g$ = Vector of supreme ground quickening,

M_b = Diagonal mass network of the unbending base,

C_b = Resultant damping framework of straight flexible confinement components,

f = Vector containing the powers assembled in the disengagement course and gadgets,

f_c = Control powers (invalid vector if there should arise an occurrence of inactive control).

A study on dynamic analysis of base isolated structure is based on two main conditions which are as follows:

- Non-sliding condition.

- Sliding condition.

Non-sliding condition: The seismic tremor reaction is a base excitation, exposed to a discretionary ground dislodging $x_g(t)$. Newton's subsequent law recommend the condition of balance [12] in those days.

$$F_I + F_D + F_S = F(t) \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where, F_I = inertia force = $m\ddot{x}_1$,

F_D = damping force = $c\dot{x}$,

$F_s = \text{elastic restoring force} = ks,$

$F(t) = \text{externally applied force} = 0.$

Sliding Condition: The sliding of the base mass starts when the sliding power conquers the frictional obstruction at the plinth level. The building now acts as a two-degree-of-freedom system and the governing differential equation of motion of the top mass can be derived from equilibrium considerations.

$$M_t (\ddot{x}_g + \ddot{x}_b + \ddot{x}_t) + C\dot{x}_t + Kx_t = 0$$

Which can be simplified as;

$$\ddot{x}_t + \ddot{x}_b + 2\varepsilon\omega_n \dot{x}_t + \omega_n^2 x_t = -\ddot{x}_g \text{-----} (6)$$

Velocity and damping ratio also play a vital role in designing earthquake resistant building:

$$V = \omega_n D = \frac{2\pi}{T_n} D$$

The pinnacle pseudo speed or pinnacle relative speed that portray by the above kinematic vitality condition. It is the relation of mass of the system m with velocity V . Velocity response is the behavior of the system against the earthquake existence in the form of velocity [13]

Now the damping ratio for concrete structures is 5% and for steel structures is 2%. Here, consider all structures made in Ahmedabad are utilizing solid material so damping proportion $\zeta = 5\%$. Damping coefficient portrays the retention of the vitality during the outer stacking.

Critical damping, $C_c = 2m\omega_n$

- Damping coefficient, $C = C_c \zeta$ [13]

After measuring damping ratio, it is necessary to calculate the deformation of a bearing or base isolated system placed in a structure.

The bearing twisting at the highest point of the conveying base or segments can be communicated as follow:

$$F_H = \frac{f}{\frac{T}{AG} + \frac{L^3}{3EI}}$$

Where, T is the bearing net thickness, A is the bearing area, G is the shear modulus, L, E and I are the carrying structural element data, FH is the horizontal force, and f is the displacement between substructure and superstructure [6].

Further, the net shaking of a structure is a joined impact of the vitality conveyed by the seismic tremor at various frequencies and the common times of the structure. Codes mirror this by the presentation of a Structural Flexibility Factor Sa/g.

As per the Indian Seismic Code IS: 1893 (Part 1) - 2007, Design Base Shear V_B is given by [14]:

$$V_B = A_h W = \frac{ZI}{2R} \left(\frac{S_a}{g} \right) W,$$

Where Z is the Seismic Zone Factor (Table 2.1), I the Importance Factor, R the Response Reduction Factor, and $\left(\frac{S_a}{g} \right)$ the Design Acceleration Spectrum Value given by:

$$\frac{S_a}{g} = \begin{cases} \begin{cases} \frac{2.5}{1.00} & 0.00 < T < 0.40 \\ \frac{2.5}{T} & 0.40 < T < 4.00 \end{cases} & \text{For soil Type I : rocky or hard soil sites} \\ \begin{cases} \frac{2.5}{1.36} & 0.00 < T < 0.55 \\ \frac{2.5}{T} & 0.55 < T < 4.00 \end{cases} & \text{For Soil Type II : medium soil sites} \\ \begin{cases} \frac{2.5}{1.67} & 0.00 < T < 0.67 \\ \frac{2.5}{T} & 0.67 < T < 4.00 \end{cases} & \text{For Soil Type III : soft soil sites} \end{cases}$$

In which T is the basic translational normal time of the structure the considered way of shaking.

3 - Case Analysis:

Introduction:

Geological conditions for Ahmedabad area

- Soil type = Medium soil (As per the geological condition)
- Zone factor (Z) = 0.16,
- Seismic zone = III,
- Seismic intensity = moderate
- Importance factor (I) = 1.5 for special type of structures,

- Other type of building = 1.0,

- Response reduction factor (R) = 3 for Ordinary RC moment-resisting frame (OMRF)

Refer [13], for the graphs for the different types of two building which have important factors of 1.0 and 1.5. These two graphs are according to the Ahmedabad condition that generated with the help of IS 1893 (Part 1): 2002.

Values taken into consideration for simulation are Peak Velocities, V_{max} , and Accelerations, A_{max} , from 26 January 2001 Bhuj Mainshock[15].

There are two cases taken into consideration for simulation as follows:

An earthquake on normal building.

An earthquake on a building with a spring box.

This is a design of one building located in Ahmedabad, bhuj earthquake zone area on which an artificial earthquake is applied to get the result.

Introduction of analysis software and calculation analysis model:

An examination of a model is finished by a product named solidworks by unique strategy. Examination on a model is completed multiple times with an alternate circumstance of a model by applying most extreme recurrence on a model.

Response Spectrum Analysis is done on a model to get the precise method of a seismic tremor vibration on a model.

Response-spectrum analysis (RSA) is a direct powerful factual investigation strategy which quantifies the commitment from every regular method of vibration to demonstrate the presumable greatest seismic reaction of a basically structure.

Calculation Results and Analysis:

Non seismic model estimation result: As there isn't a putting of a tremor resistive gadget in a model there is more harm because of vibration brought about by reaction range technique as a vibration of quake it tends to be finished up by relocation and mass investment of a model on

various frequencies, Greatest relocation esteem = 1.154e mm And maximum mass participation on a model from all axes =

Sum X = 0.42593	Sum Y = 0.09169	Sum Z = 0.49654
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On normal recurrence of 70 Hertz.

Count aftereffect of an Isolation model: Similarly a model with a tremor resistive proof structure is put under reaction range investigation strategy to acquire the pinnacle limit of a structure on an equivalent recurrence.

Accordingly, greatest relocation esteem is 5.630e-012mm and maximum mass participation on a model from all axes=

Sum X =.00940988	Sum Y =0.028326201	Sum Z = 0.132116468
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Contrast analysis of two result: By contrasting both the outcome plainly there is change in values in both the models. As a model without quake resistive plan cause more harm on a structure during vibration impact on it contrasted with the other structure, Indeed, even plainly the model with a tremor resistive structure have less mass support which means can uncovered more burden and vibration impact contrasted with other structure.

An analysis of an earthquake on normal building.

Study properties:

Study name = Dynamic 1

Form of Analysis = Dynamic linear analysis (Spectrum Response Analysis)

Mesh type = Solid Mesh

Number of frequencies = 20

Solver type = FFE Plus

Soft Spring = off

Incompatible bonding options = Automatic

Thermal option = Include temperature loads

Zero strain temperature = 298 Kelvin

Material properties:

Figure 1.1- A normal building

Name: Concrete
Model type: Linear Elastic Isotropic
Default failure criterion: Unknown
Tensile strength: $5e+006 \text{ N/m}^2$
Compressive strength: $4e+007 \text{ N/m}^2$
Elastic modulus: $4.1e+010 \text{ N/m}^2$
Poisson's ratio: 0.21
Mass density: 2400 kg/m^3
Material damping ratio: 0.05

Load and fixtures:

Fixture name = Fixed-1

Fixture Image =

Fixture Details = Entities: 1 face(S)

Type = Fixed geometry.

Resultant forces =

<i>Component s</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>Y</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>Resultant</i>
<i>Reaction force(N)</i>	1.25959e+00 6	4.81576e+00 6	2.08035e+00 6	5.395e+00 6
<i>Reaction Moment (N.m)</i>	0	0	0	0

Mesh information:

Mesh type = Solid Mesh

Mesh type = Curvature-based mesh

Jacobian points = 4 Points

Maximum element size = 0.643472 m

Minimum element size = 0.643472 m

Mesh Quality Plot = High

Mesh-information details:

Total Nodes = 21650

Total Elements = 11016

Maximum Aspect Ratio = 9233.1

Percentage of Aspect Ratio < 3 = 13.2

% of distorted elements (Jacobian) = 1.73

% of distorted elements (Jacobian) = 0

Figure 1.2- Mesh information

Sensor details:

Sensor name = Minimum Factor of Safety1

Sensor details = Result: Factor of Safety

Component: Automatic

Criterion: Model Max

Step Criterion: Across all Steps

Step No.:1

Alert Value: is less than 2

Location =

Figure 1.3- Location of an applied earthquake.

Study result:

Stress value:

Name = Stress

Type = VON: von Mises Stress

Min = 1.655e+000N/m²

Node: 10121

Max = 1.631e+007N/m²

Node: 5045

Figure 1.4- stress value

Displacement value:

Name = Displacement

Type = URES: Resultant Displacement

Min = 0.000e+000mm

Node: 104

Max = 1.154e+000mm

Node: 316

Figure 1.5- Displacement value

Mass participation:

Number mode	Spectrum (Hertz)	X path	Y path	Z path
1..19	69.419	0.00023799	0.021581	0.019783
20	70.793	0.0006876	0.003481	0.00011676
		Sum X = 0.42593	Sum Y = 0.09169	Sum Z = 0.49654

I. An analysis of an earthquake on a building with a spring box (earthquake resistant building):

Now a building with a spring box:

Study properties:

Study name	Dynamic 1
Analysis type	Linear dynamic analysis (Response Spectrum Analysis)

Mesh type	Solid Mesh
Number of frequencies	10
Solver type	Direct sparse solver
Soft Spring:	Off
Incompatible bonding options	Simplified
Thermal option	Include temperature loads
Zero strain temperature	298 Kelvin
Incorporate liquid weight impacts from SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation	Off
Mode combination method	Square root sum of squares (SRSS)
Result folder	SOLIDWORKS document (C:\3D Model Of Building\Spring Box)

**Placing of spring box in a building as a base-isolation system:
Floor plan: - Model:**

Figure 2.1

Figure 2.2

Load and fixtures:

Fixture Image:

Figure 2.3

Fixture name	Fixture Details			
Fixed-1	Entities: 61 face(s) Type: Fixed Geometry			
Resultant Forces:				
<i>Components</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>Y</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>Resultant</i>
Reaction force(N)	5.3297 1e-011	2.2438 8e-010	5.2069 1e-011	2.36436 e-010
Reaction Moment (N.m)	0	0	0	0

Load Image:

Figure 2.4

Load name	Load Details
Base Excitation-1	<p style="text-align: center;">Type: Acceleration</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Translation: ---, ---, 1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Units: mm</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Phase Angle: 0</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Units: deg</p>

Frequency curve:

Figure 2.5

Study result:

Stress value:

Name= Stress

Type= VON: von Mises Stress

Min= 0.000e+000N/m² Node: 1

Max= 3.532e-007N/m² Node: 1041620

Figure 2.6 – Stress Value

Displacement Value:

Name= Displacement

Type= URES: Resultant Displacement

Min= 0.000e+000mm Node: 1

Max= 5.630e-012mm Node: 573075

Figure 2.7- Displacement Value

Mass participation:

Mode Number	spectrum (Hertz)	X path	Y path	Z path
1..9	70.402	0.002410164	0.003497746	0.058537064
10	70.94	0.002383544	0.003471219	0.03458938
		Sum X =.00940988	Sum Y =0.028326201	Sum Z = 0.132116468

Conclusion

- According to the stress and displacement values taken out from simulation of both the cases it can be stated that the damage by earthquake in a building without spring box is 27% percent and damage in a building with a spring box is approx. 27%.
- The resultant difference in percentage of damage by earthquake to a building is approx. 27%. So, it is clearly seen that a use of spring in a building can perfectly work as an earthquake resistive device.
- A utilization of spring box is the best compelling approach to diminish the auxiliary harm in a structure by any regular peril like tremor. A reproduction-based test is done right now applying straight powerful irregular vibration on a structure as a seismic tremor of the force from past quake esteems.
- Because of recreation by straight powerful having irregular vibration and reaction range investigation test on both the structure the mass interest was distinctive on both the structure which shows that a structure without base detachment framework have more harm contrasted with working with a base disconnection gadget by approx. 27% contrast.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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